

made to prepare other exchangers² showing special selectivities for certain ions. Recently zirconium sulphophosphate, $[\text{Zr}(\text{O}_3\text{PC}_6\text{H}_5\text{SOH})_x(\text{HPO}_4)_{2-x}\cdot\text{YH}_2\text{O}]$ has been prepared and characterised³.

Considering the fact that the presence of carboxyl groups in basic zirconium phosphate network provides exchangers of special selective properties for certain ions, attempts have been made to prepare and characterise a new inorganic exchanger zirconium succinophosphate (ZrSP) in presence of succinic acid.

Experimental

Infrared spectra was obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 541 spectrophotometer. A Phillips diffractometer was used to get the X-ray diffraction pattern using nickel filtered Cu-K radiations. Thermogravimetric data was obtained by using a Stanton's thermo-balance with a heating rate of 4° per min. All reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

Separation of zirconium succinophosphate: To a solution of zirconyl nitrate in nitric acid (7.6 g in 56 ml 1.0 M acid) a solution of succinic acid (slightly > 1.0 M) in sodium hydroxide (2.0 M) was added with constant stirring. The resulting thick white precipitate of the complexed zirconium compound was quickly poured into phosphoric acid (0.62 N; 50 ml) and stirred vigorously for ~0.5 h. Precipitate so obtained was washed with distilled water till free from nitrate ions and then (Compound-A) was dried at 100°. The dried solid was again submerged in water, grounded, filtered and dried at 100°. Samples for studying the effect of temperature were prepared similarly but were dried at room temperature (~20°). Compound-A was an amorphous gel type exchanger with initial ratio of Zr : organic acid : PO₄ as 1 : 1 : 1. Similar preparations were done with initial reactant ratios of (B) 1 : 0.5 : 1, (C) 1 : 1.5 : 1 and (D) 1 : 2.0 : 1. They were all used to compare their limiting exchange capacities only. In all subsequent studies only compound-A was used.

Determination of ion-exchange capacity: The limiting exchange capacity of compounds A, B, C and D were first obtained in neutral solutions by using 1.0 N NaCl solution in sufficient excess using static method. Similar capacity determination was also made on compound-A heated to different temperatures and heated to 100° at different pH values.

Results and Discussion

Chemical stability: The chemical stability of the exchanger was observed in mineral acids (HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄) and bases (NaOH, NH₄OH) at concentrations 0.1, 0.25, 0.50, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 N. The exchanger (0.25 g) was equilibrated with the acid or alkali solution (50 ml) and left as such for 24 h. The solutions were then analysed for the released phosphate and also for zirconium ions separately. The exchanger was found to be stable in acid solutions

Zirconium Succinophosphate – A New Inorganic Cation-exchanger

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THE preparation and the ion-exchange properties of several amorphous zirconium compounds have been investigated¹. Still zirconium phosphate stands out as a unique product of highest stability and ion-exchange capacity. Based on the initial network of zirconium phosphate, attempts have been

upto 0.5 *N* and in alkali solutions upto 0.1 *N* concentrations. Alkali solutions at 0.25 *N* eluted phosphate ions appreciably and this increased with the increase in alkali concentration. No decomposition of the exchanger with respect to zirconium ion release was observed upto 1.0 *N* acidity.

Stability towards heat: This was observed not only in terms of the change in exchange capacity but also by observing change in colour of the sample. No outward indication of decomposition was found upto 250°. The white product changed to light yellow at 300° and became yellowish black at 400°. This clearly indicate setting-in of the decomposition of the organic moiety at ~300°. The product became perfectly white again at ~1000° and analysis proved it to be $ZrP_2O_7(ZrO_2.P_2O_5)$.

Selectivity study for univalent cations in zirconium succinophosphate: Such study was carried out with the exchanger (0.25 g) and electrolyte solution (50 ml) equilibrated for 24 h with constant stirring. The extent of exchange was determined titrimetrically either by estimating the released acidity or the metal ion. The selectivity coefficient was obtained for alkali metal ion, Ag^+ and Tl^+ using the relationship given by Kressman and Kitchener⁴, which was corrected to get *K* (corrected) by graphical integration. The results show the selectivity sequence for univalent ion as $Li^+ < Na^+ < K^+ < Ag^+ < Tl^+ < Cs^+$.

Distribution data: Ion-exchange distribution of a large number of ions was also obtained under equilibrium conditions by batch technique at macro-level concentrations (0.1 *N*). Table I reports the K_D values. The exchanger appeared to show some preference for Ba^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Th^{4+} ions.

TABLE I—WEIGHT DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS OF IONS OF ZrSP

Ion	Ionic concn. <i>M</i>	K_D	Ion	Ionic concn.	K_D
Li^+	0.1	5.1	Mg^{2+}	0.089	3.4
Na^+	0.1	6.2	Cu^{2+}	0.100	4.2
K^+	0.1	6.2	Zn^{2+}	0.088	3.8
Rb^+	0.1	7.5	Fe^{2+}	0.088	12.8
Cs^+	0.1	8.1	Co^{2+}	0.079	6.7
NH_4^+	0.1	6.2	Ni^{2+}	0.085	4.0
Ag^+	0.1	6.6	La^{3+}	0.086	10.4
Tl^+	0.1	7.2	Ce^{3+}	0.430	5.5
Ca^{2+}	0.1	4.0	Th^{4+}	0.120	31.8
Sr^{2+}	0.1	4.4	U^{6+}	0.086	6.7
Ba^{2+}	0.1	16.2	—	—	—

The inorganic exchanger, zirconium succinophosphate appears to be a better exchanger than a simple zirconium phosphate gel prepared under identical conditions. It gives a maximum exchange capacity of 6.7 meq/g at pH 10–11. The limiting exchange capacity in neutral solutions (pH 7.0) is ~0.8 meq/g which decreases with decreasing pH and increases with higher pH of the solution. A

sample of the exchanger when heated up to 100° does not lose its exchange capacity, however, with increasing temperature the capacity decreases considerably with simultaneous changes in the physical state of the exchanger. Thus it is quite stable upto 200° but it decomposes slowly till it attains a simple pyrophosphate composition $ZrO_2.P_2O_5$ at ~1000°. However, from the point of view of its use as an exchanger, a heated sample upto 100° is good in its form (granular) and constancy of exchange capacity. Its chemical stability is also satisfactory in moderately acidic (upto 0.5 *N*) and alkaline (upto 0.1 *N*) solutions.

The chemical analysis of compound-A prepared initially with 1 : 1 : 1 ratio of Zr : organic acid : PO_4 though gave $ZrO_2 : P_2O_5$ ratio as 1 : 1.13 (or ~1 : 1), but the mole ratio for the organic part as evaluated from carbon estimation was obtained as 0.5 per zirconium atom. Hence the organic molecule may be expected to be involved in the $-Zr-O-Zr-$ chain structure (1) which has been supported by ir and thermogravimetric data.

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The coordination to each zirconium (coordination number 6) is completed by adding up one H_2O molecule to each one of them.

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